

Co-creation from the South: The case of Cyprus

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1. Introduction

In Greek-Cypriot, postcolonial society, the modernist ideals of the 20th century have largely influenced planning institutions that give shape to the urban landscape. Moreover, the dominance of private real-estate development industries in Nicosia and the coastal cities of the island is physically manifested by the incessant parcellation of land, opportunistic development and various forms of peri-urban growth with interconnected socio-environmental implications (Constantinides, 2018; Ioannou, 2016). More democratic and equitable processes of urban development are urgently needed with a focus on the increased participation of citizens as co-creators of urban knowledge. However, contemporary literature argues that urban theory from the global North can no longer be simply copied and applied to the global South. Instead, new urban theory engages with the heterogeneous realities of different contexts. This is particularly relevant to the burgeoning theory and practices of citizen participation and co-creation in urban planning in Europe. This paper investigates the weaknesses and opportunities of active civic engagement in housing and neighbourhood development matters in the Greek-Cypriot context of Southern Europe. Finally, it concludes with recommendations in applying the methodology of Urban Living Labs in order to facilitate inclusiveness and co-creation in planning in 'Southern' regions.

2. Research work

In the period of rapid urbanisation in Cyprus during the 1950s and '60s and more recently, in post-crisis construction busts and booms, private property ownership has been the dominant driver in decisions about urban land. These trajectories of urban development involve the promotion of individual home ownership and the construction of infrastructure mainly in the interest of further capital accumulation by the development industry. More recent efforts to attract foreign investment, by large scale property developments and luxury housing, are arguably widening the state-citizen gap in decisions about housing. Furthermore, urban governance has been in these ways very much *infrastructure-led* (Ekers et al., 2012) and *property-led*, and therefore, in accordance with global trends of urban growth.

However, in contrast to many industrialised Western European countries, suburban expansion in postcolonial Cyprus did not take place in the form of large-scale housing developments backed by state policies. Instead, "spontaneous urban development" and urban informality, as in other South European cities (Leontidou, 1990), characterise the organisation of housing and land uses. In addition, dominated by a technocratic state and a form of "Greek-Cypriot corporatism" (Mavratsas, 1998), civil society has been found to be underdeveloped (CIVICUS, 2011). Accordingly, a lack of citizen participation and the lack of power to negotiate decisions about urban development is reflected by the many people dwelling and working in the margins between powerful state and market actors. Informal and co-produced urban spaces (here understood as spontaneously co-produced) by actors who "do not typically fit into state-

led and ‘professional’ planning schemes” (Galuszka, 2019, p. 144) are common, yet not recognised or institutionalised. These characteristics place Cyprus in the discussions around citizenship and participation in the global South.

In the meantime, new urban governance arrangements are on the agenda of many European governments promoting “active citizenship” and social innovation concerning the decision-making processes that involve citizens in the planning and provision of housing and public services (Bisschops & Beunen, 2019; Boonstra, 2015; Garcia & Haddock, 2016; Morgan, 2018). Also, opportunities for new infrastructure networks and governance arrangements that reshape power imbalances particularly exist in the suburbs (Filion & Keil, 2017; Hamel & Keil, 2016). In these views the suburbs are cast as fertile “laboratories” for fostering alternatives to dominant governance coalitions that have determined housing and infrastructure. The case of Oosterwold in the Netherlands is one prominent example (Cozzolino et al., 2017).

Furthermore, recent research is increasingly emphasising *co-creation* (Davis & Andrew, 2017; Koster, 2015) – the sharing of decision-making powers between municipalities, citizens and other actors – and this term is being applied in housing development and urban regeneration experiments at the neighbourhood scale. Innovative governance processes encouraging self-organisation to engage citizens beyond participation in planning are being investigated in settings labelled by the terms Urban Living Labs (ULLs), city labs or citizen innovation labs. In ULLs the joint knowledge and abilities of citizens, urban professionals, and local authorities is mobilised in collaborative environments where innovation can take place in real-life settings. Temporary settings of experimentation provide opportunities for exploring different paths to institutional norms by prioritising collaboration among stakeholders.

However, as these novel approaches are being transferred mainly from Northern cities to Southern Europe, there is a need to investigate co-creation by “seeing from the South” (Watson, 2009) and to avoid the mistake of applying a universal concept to contexts which to date have been perceived at the fringes of urbanity. In support of the “peripheral turn” in urban studies, it is important to challenge general guidelines that are replicated, including ULLs, and to adapt these novel governance approaches to their respective contexts (Galuszka, 2019). The ways in which civic engagement is fostered in Cyprus, especially regarding matters of urban development and informality, will form the main research question. How are processes and methods of citizen participation in planning influenced by socio-cultural traits?

Interviews will be conducted with a civil society group who deal with community engagement and urban regeneration in Nicosia, with municipality employees and with staff of NGOs involved in the Active Citizens Fund Cyprus Programme (Outcome 1, “Increased Citizen Participation in Civic Activities”). An online questionnaire will also be used to collect data from citizens in order to investigate how the different path-dependent, political, economic and cultural histories that are entangled with home ownership and neighbourhood development patterns, may affect the opportunities and needs for co-creation in urban planning. Available secondary data regarding citizen participation in planning will be examined.

3. Conclusion

This paper aims to add to the theoretical discussion of co-creation, social innovation and active citizenship from a “southern” perspective, including the overlapping interpretations of the global South and Southern Europe. It will challenge existing parameters and guidelines of civic engagement and innovation in urban planning and housing by exploring the need to develop a southern perspective of co-creation. The goal is to enhance the diversity of southern

perspectives of urban theory, to challenge assumptions around best practices of sustainable urban development, but also to improve the methodology of applying co-creation to tackle housing and planning issues in postcolonial contexts.

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